

Sepedon sphegeus (Fabr.)(Sciomyzidae) and Notiphila spp. (Ephydriidae): alternate hosts of Trichogramma japonicum Ashmead, a rice stem borer egg parasite

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In the Philippines, *Trichogramma japonicum* Ashmead is a common egg parasite of rice stem borers *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *Chilo suppressalis*, and *C. polychrysus*. Eggs of two genera of flies that inhabit rice fields —*Sepedon sphegeus* (Fabr.) (Sciomyzidae) and *Notiphila latigenis* Hendel, *N. similis* Meijere and *N. spinosa* Cresson (Ephydriidae) — were collected in the field in 1981-82 in six provinces. *T. japonicum* occurred in at least one fly species (see table). *Sepedon* and *Notiphila* lay egg masses on rice leaves in a similar manner as the rice stem borer. *Trichogramma* wasps encounter both. Even though fly eggs are much larger than stem borer eggs they are acceptable to the wasps. Low rates of parasitization in fly eggs indicate that stem borer eggs are preferred. But such alternate hosts as these two fly genera would maintain *Trichogramma* in the field at times of low stem borer populations, enhancing its effectiveness as a natural enemy of stemborers.

Incidence of parasitization by *Trichogramma japonicum* on eggs of *Sepedon sphegeus* and *Notiphila* spp. collected from six fields in the Philippines, 1981-82.

Province	Municipality	Sampling date	<i>Sepedon sphegeus</i>		<i>Notiphila</i> spp. ^{a/}	
			Eggs held (no.)	Parasitization (%)	Eggs held (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Cagayan	Solana	23 Sep 1981	6	0	14	14.3
Laguna	Los Baños	23-27 Nov 1981	11	36.4	52	8.0
		7-17 Dec 1981	5	20.0	181	2.0
		18-29 Jan 1982	18	5.5	162	7.4
		8-24 Feb 1982	23	8.3	234	10.3
Agusan del Sur	Del Monte	26 Jul 1981	0	-	24	0.0
Bukidnon	Kalilangan	29 Jul 1981	0	-	36	6.0
North Cotabato	Kabacan	4-6 Jan 1982	0	-	22	5.0
Zamboanga del Sur	Pagadian	3-4 Aug 1981	0	0	18	-

^{a/} *Notiphila latigenis* Hendel, *N. similis* Meijere, and *N. spinosa* Cresson.

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